

Analysis of Electrodes Material Performance in Hydrogen Production using Electrolysis of Alkaline Water

Ayesha M-Jumma*, Nizamudin Baloch, Samar Ali, Dua Nizam

Department of Chemistry, University of Balochistan, Quetta, Pakistan

ARTICLE: INFO

Keywords:

*Electrolysis,
Green Hydrogen Production,
Electrode Materials.*

History:

Received 17 February 2026

Accepted 29 March 2026

Published 05 April 2026

ABSTRACT

The hydrogen is a green energy source which is replacing the convention fossil fuel to generate energy. Alkaline water electrolysis is used to produce hydrogen which is safe and considered to be stands out as a mature and scalable technology for hydrogen generation. In this reserach we have analyze the effect of electrode materials on the production of hydrogen using electrolysis of water. Two electrodes steel and aluminum were used for alkalis NaOH comparison of Hydrogen production via different concentration. From results it was revealed that the steel electrode is more suitable in terms of current density vs cell voltage performance of two electrolyte based alkaline water electrolysis. Finally for longer life performance, the temperature of the solution is the parameter. The temperature of steel electrode cell much stable than the aluminum which makes it more suitable for long life and resistant to corrosion.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern life, energy is essential and plays a vital role in modern world. The energy use of the world is rising day by day [1]. Currently, a significant portion of the world's electricity is still generated by fossil fuels. The stocks of fossil fuel are limited and are being depleted rapidly due to rising consumption [2]. Despite of their limited availability, use of fossil fuels contributes to environmental issues such as greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution. To compensate these impacts, renewable and sustainable energy sources are increasingly being considered. Among them,

hydrogen fuel has emerged as a clean and efficient alternative. Hydrogen fuel is produced through a process called water electrolysis, where electricity splits water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen gases. An electrolyte is added to the water to enable the reaction, which is entirely carbon-free, as no carbon-based compounds are involved or produced [3]. A key benefit of hydrogen fuel is its ability to generate power without emitting any harmful gases. When using hydrogen fuel cell technology, the process is significantly more efficient than traditional fossil fuel methods reported to be two to three times as efficient.

Corresponding author. Ayesha M-Jumma *

E-mail address: ayishamjumma@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19548664>

Specifically, a typical hydrogen fuel cell can achieve an efficiency of approximately 60%, whereas conventional fuel generators generally operate at efficiencies between 33% and 35% [4]. In addition to these benefits, significant challenges remain, including high overpotentials, catalyst degradation, and inherent system inefficiencies. For hydrogen production, alkaline electrolyzers are a frequent choice because of their lower cost and the ready availability of suitable alkaline electrolytes. However, optimizing production requires careful control, as both the concentration and the temperature of the electrolyte are critical variables that directly influence hydrogen generation via electrolysis [5]. An important factor which affects the parameters like efficiency, durability and economic viability is the electrode material used in alkaline water analysis. The selection of the typical electrode used directly impacts the life, energy consumption and other important parameters [6]. Traditionally, noble metals such as platinum and iridium have demonstrated excellent electrocatalytic properties; however, their high cost and scarcity drive the need for alternative materials with comparable performance [7-8]. The electrode material plays an important role in the production of hydrogen via electrolysis. Current electrodes often face limitations like high over potentials, poor catalytic activity, low durability, and high cost, which hinder large-scale adoption of this technology. Despite the ongoing research, there is a need to investigate the commercially available low-cost metals for analyzing the efficient hydrogen production via electrolysis of alkaline water. In this paper we have analyzed the performance of steel and aluminum electrodes.

II. METHODOLOGY

Cell Design:

For hydrogen generation, the cell design used is depicted in figure 1. The electrodes are made from rectangular steel plates. Steel and aluminum which are mechanically robust to stain, good electrical conductor. A simple rectangular geometry was used for cell design. Each steel plate with dimension 13cm by 8cm was used for cell fabrication.

Figure 1 Cell design for hydrogen generation

For each cell 2 steel sheets were used. Plates are separated by using a 2cm plastic separator.

The cell is used in vertical mode for electrolysis in parallel set up. Inter electrode spacing was put as about 2cm between one plate and the other. The implemented system is shown in figure 2. A semi permeable membrane is made using silk cloth to prevent the recombination of hydrogen and oxygen produced at electrodes. The membrane separates the cell into two sections. The section containing anode collects oxygen and the other section with cathode collects hydrogen. Finally outlet holes are drilled to each section to obtain the hydrogen and oxygen from the outlets.

Figure 2 Implemented steel cell for hydrogen generation

Electrolyte preparation:

For electrolysis alkaline solutions are used due to the oxygen and hydrogen emission mechanism. Two alkalis, NaOH and KOH were selected for the optimal concentration performance. We prepared NaOH solution of 1 Molar and 2 Molar. Both KOH and NaOH was selected due to its strong ionic conductivity and usefulness in speeding up the process of electrolysis.

Solar Powered Electrolysis:

For green generation of hydrogen, the experimental was carried out by using a solar panel, a source of energy as shown in Figure 3, the electrolysis setup can be used with and without solar panel. The panel generates an output of 21 volts which was down converted to 12V using buck converter.

Figure 3 Electrolysis setup with solar panel

Chemical Reactions:

When we dissolve NaOH in water, it disintegrate into its Na^+ and OH^- ions as shown by

Overall the reaction is given by

Similarly when KOH is dissolved into water it generates K^+ and OH^- ions

Overall the reaction is given by

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research, we have used the steel electrode cell and aluminum electrode cell with NaOH with concentration of 2 mole, KOH with concentrations of 1 and 2 mole respectively.

Performance of steel and aluminum cell for 2 molar NaOH:

The curve of figure 4 shows the performance of steel cell and aluminum using 2 molar solution. It is evident from curve 'steel' figure 4 that the cell voltage for steel cell increases from 3V to 5.56V. The corresponding current density changes from 57.0 mA/cm^2 to 20.3 mA/cm^2 . The second curve "Aluminum" of the shows the cell voltage variations from 3.3 to 6.9V. The corresponding values of current density varies from 59.0 mA/cm^2 to 233.0 mA/cm^2 . The greater cell voltage corresponds to increase in resistance due to oxidation on electrodes.

Figure 4 Current density vs Cell voltage at 2 molar NaOH solution for steel and aluminum electrodes

It is further observed from the graph that with the increase of the hydrogen production for aluminum is greater than steel.

Performance of steel and aluminum cell for 1 molar KOH:

The curve of figure 5 shows the performance of steel cell and aluminum using 1 molar KOH solution. It is evident from curve 'steel' figure 5 that the cell voltage for steel cell increases from 2.5V to 3.2V. The corresponding current density changes from 59.0 mA/cm^2 to 216.0 mA/cm^2 . The second curve "Aluminum" of the figure 5 shows the cell voltage variations from 2.8 to 5.2V. The corresponding values of current density varies from 60.0 mA/cm^2 to 236.0 mA/cm^2 . The greater cell voltage corresponds to increase in resistance due to oxidation on electrodes.

Figure 5 Current density vs Cell voltage at 1 molar KOH solution for steel and aluminum electrodes

It is further observed from the graph that with the increase of the hydrogen production for aluminum is greater than steel.

[I] Performance of steel and aluminum cell for 2 molar KOH.

The curve of Figure 6 shows the performance of steel cell and aluminum using 2 molar KOH solution. It is evident from curve 'steel' figure 6 that the cell voltage for steel cell increases from 2.29V to 3.0V. The corresponding current density changes from 47.0 mA/cm^2 to 200.0 mA/cm^2 . The second curve "Aluminum" of the figure 6 shows the cell voltage variations from 2.4V to 5.4V. The corresponding values of current density varies from 49.0 mA/cm^2 to 230.0 mA/cm^2 . The greater cell voltage corresponds to increase in resistance due to oxidation on electrodes.

Figure 6 Current density vs Cell voltage at 2 molar KOH solution for steel and aluminum electrodes

It is further observed from the graph that with the increase of the hydrogen production for aluminum is greater than steel.

Temperature vs cell voltage performance:

For both cells i.e. steel and aluminum the temperatures of the electrolytes were recorded during the experiment. It was observed. Figure 7 depicts the cell voltage vs temperature graph at 2 molar solution of NaOH both for steel and aluminum

Figure 7 Cell voltage vs temperature at 1.5 molar NaOH solution

Figure 7 depicts the cell voltage vs temperature graph at 1 molar KOH solution. From the curve “Steel” and “Aluminum”, it is concluded that the temperature of steel based cell is much less compared to cell with aluminum electrodes.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, we have analyze the effect of electrode material on the production of hydrogen using electrolysis of water. Two alkalis NaOH and KOH were selected to perform the comparison of Hydrogen production via different electrodes. From results of Figure 4.1 the performance of steel cell and aluminum using 2 molar solution. It is evident from the results that the cell voltage for steel cell increases from 3V to 5.56V. The corresponding current density changes from 57.0 mA/cm² to 203.0 mA/cm². The second curve “Aluminum” shows the cell voltage variations from 3.3 to 6.9V. The corresponding values of current density varies from 59.0 mA/cm² to 233.0 mA/cm². The greater cell voltage corresponds to increase in resistance due to oxidation on electrodes. Similar results were observed for KOH with 2 molar concentration. Finally for longer life performance, the temperature of the solution is the parameter. The temperature vs cell voltage curve revealed that the steel cell is more stable and perform better interns of corrosion stability which makes it suitable for long life use in hydrogen production.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kreuter, W., & Hofmann, H. (1998). Electrolysis: the important energy transformer in a world of sustainable energy. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 23(8), 661-666
- [2] Hu W 2000, “Electrocatalytic properties of new electrocatalysts for hydrogen evolution in alkaline water electrolysis”, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy* 25: 111-118
- [3] Choi H, Shin J, Woo J (2018) Effect of electricity generation mix on battery electric vehicle adoption and its environmental impact. *Energy Policy* 121:13–24.
- [4] Razmi, A. R., Alirahmi, S. M., Nabat, M. H., Assareh, E., & Shahbakhti, M. (2022). A green hydrogen energy storage concept based on parabolic trough collector and proton exchange membrane electrolyzer/fuel cell: thermodynamic and exergoeconomic analyses with multi-objective optimization. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 47(62), 26468-26489.
- [5] Singla, M. K., Nijhawan, P., & Oberoi, A. S. (2021). Hydrogen fuel and fuel cell technology for cleaner future: a review. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(13), 15607-15626.
- [6] Vinod, M. P., Gopinath, C. S., & Sreekumar, K. (2020). Electrode materials for water electrolysis: Current status and future challenges. *Catalysis Reviews*, 62(3), 339–406.
- [7] Döscher, H., Geisz, J. F., Deutsch, T. G., & Turner, J. A. (2014). Sunlight absorption in water—efficiency and design implications for photoelectrochemical devices. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 7(9), 2951-2956.
- [8] Khan, S., Sohail, M., & Bokhari, M. (2024). Green Hydrogen Production using Electrolysis via Renewable Energy. *Journal of Nano-scope*, 5(2), 137-145.

